

The Influence of Influencer Marketing and Product Innovation on Purchase Decisions in the Fashion MSMEs Veilish.chic in Tulungagung Regency

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the influence of influencer marketing and product innovation on consumer purchase decisions at the fashion MSMEs Veilish.chic, located in Tulungagung Regency. The research method employed is quantitative, based on a sample of 100 respondents collected using purposive sampling. Data were collected through questionnaires and analyzed using multiple linear regression. The results showed that influencer marketing and product innovation have a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. Influencer marketing has the highest regression coefficient (0.738), followed by product innovation (0.699). These results suggest that the consistent and continuous implementation of influencer marketing strategies and product innovation can enhance consumer purchase decisions. The study provides practical implications for business actors to carefully select influencers who are not only popular but also capable of delivering product information effectively, as well as to continuously innovate and introduce new products to maintain consumer interest and product relevance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Veilish.chic is one of the emerging fashion MSMEs (Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises) in Tulungagung Regency that has shown positive growth. The brand offers a variety of unique, trendy, and fashionable women's clothing models that are tailored to market needs, especially targeting younger consumers. Despite being relatively new, Veilish.chic has achieved a significant increase in sales, growing from 2% to 46%, and has gained recognition in various regions across Indonesia through effective digital marketing strategies. This positive phenomenon is noteworthy for further study as it demonstrates that the success of an MSMEs does not solely depend on how long the business has been established, but also on the implementation of appropriate marketing strategies using digital media and continuous product innovation (Ghassani et al., 2022). These indications highlight the need for a more in-depth analysis of the role of influencer marketing and product innovation in influencing consumer purchasing decisions in the digital era, particularly within the fashion MSMEs sector.

One of the most influential digital marketing strategies in the modern era is influencer marketing, where companies collaborate with influential individuals on social media. This approach now represents a promising new opportunity, as it is considered one of the fastest-growing tools for acquiring new customers online (Nadanyiova and Sujanska, 2023). Based on observations, it was found that Veilish.chic became widely recognized after partnering with influencers who had a large number of followers, allowing them to influence their audience's purchasing behavior. This observation is supported by the opinion of Hodijah et al. (2021), who state that influencer marketing is a promotional strategy that leverages social media to facilitate the purchasing process and enhance consumer trust. The influence of an influencer can make the message conveyed more effective and easily accepted by consumers, ultimately leading to purchasing decisions.

In addition to influencer marketing, fashion business owners must also continuously engage in product innovation to remain competitive in the market (Maulina et al., 2024). Observations show that Veilish.chic consistently innovates by offering fashionable women's clothing that aligns with current youth trends and possesses unique features that reflect the brand's identity. This is

supported by Saputro and Widyastuti (2022), who argued that companies are required to innovate continuously, as those that fail to do so will not be able to compete in the marketplace.

Based on these observations, it can be concluded that factors such as influencer marketing and product innovation play a significant role in influencing consumer purchasing decisions, especially for fashion MSMEs in the digital age. Therefore, this study is conducted to analyze the extent to which influencer marketing and product innovation affect consumer purchasing decisions at Veilish.chic. This research is important as it aims to contribute to the development of effective digital marketing strategies for MSMEs, particularly in the fashion sector, to remain sustainable and competitive in a highly dynamic market. Furthermore, the results of this study are expected to serve as a reference for other business owners in designing effective and innovative marketing strategies to enhance product appeal and drive consumer purchasing decisions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Influencer Marketing

According to Smuda (2018:6), influencer marketing is defined as a marketing strategy that utilizes individuals on social media to influence consumer purchasing decisions. Influencers serve as modern opinion leaders who recommend products or services, initiate brand communication in the form of electronic word of mouth (eWOM), and continuously impact an organization's commercial performance.

Furthermore, Smuda (2018:9) identifies three key indicators of influencer marketing: trustworthiness, expertise, and attractiveness.

Product Innovation

According to Sudarmanto (2022:52), product innovation refers to the efforts made by business actors to improve, enhance, develop, and refine the products they have been producing. Innovation activities include product development, product improvement, entirely new developments, and the expansion of the company's product lines. The products developed may consist of goods or services, with the aim of making them better than before.

Furthermore, Sudarmanto (2022:60) explains that there are five indicators of product innovation, namely: the development of new products, new product lines, additions to existing product lines, improvements to existing products, and cost reduction.

Purchase Decision

According to Indrasari (2019:70), a purchase decision is defined as a selection between two or more alternative choices, where alternatives must be available for a person to make a decision. Conversely, if a consumer has no alternatives to choose from and is completely forced to make a particular purchase and take a specific action, then such a situation cannot be considered a decision.

The indicators of a purchase decision, according to Kotler and Keller as translated by Tjiptono (2012:184) in Indrasari (2019:74), consist of five sub-decisions: product choice, brand choice, dealer choice, purchase timing, and purchase quantity.

Hypothesis Formulation

H₁ : It is suspected that influencer marketing has a positive partial effect on purchase decisions for fashion MSMEs products of Veilish.chic in Tulungagung Regency.

Research conducted by Wilis and Faik (2022) found that influencer marketing has a positive effect on purchase decisions. In contrast, the findings of Syahputri et al. (2024) revealed that influencer marketing has a negative effect on purchase decisions.

H₂ : It is suspected that product innovation has a positive partial effect on purchase decisions for fashion MSMEs products of Veilish.chic in Tulungagung Regency.

Research conducted by Octaviani and Batu (2022) found that product innovation has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. However, the study conducted by Vitantri, et al., (2022) showed that product innovation does not have a significant effect on purchasing decisions.

H₃ : It is suspected that influencer marketing and product innovation have a simultaneous positive effect on purchase decisions for fashion MSMEs products of Veilish.chic in Tulungagung Regency.

Research conducted by Ghassani et al. (2022) found that influencer marketing and product innovation have a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions.

III. METHOD

This research is an explanatory study using a quantitative approach. According to Sugiyono (2019:16–17), a quantitative approach is used to study a specific population or sample and to test predetermined hypotheses. The purpose of this study is to analyze the influence of influencer marketing and product innovation on purchase decisions of fashion MSMEs products from

Veilish.chic in Tulungagung Regency. This study employs multiple linear regression analysis to test the hypotheses, and the results are interpreted to address the research questions and draw conclusions.

The population of this study consists of all consumers of Veilish.chic, with a sample of 100 respondents selected through purposive sampling, which is the selection of samples based on specific characteristics (Riyanto & Hatmawan, 2020:17). The criteria for respondents include consumers aged 17–30 years who have purchased Veilish.chic products during the 2022–2024 period, have seen promotional content from influencers on Instagram, and are familiar with the various product innovations introduced by Veilish.chic.

Data were collected using a questionnaire consisting of statements related to influencer marketing, product innovation, and purchase decisions, measured using a five-point Likert scale. The research instrument was tested for validity and reliability, followed by descriptive analysis, classical assumption testing, multiple linear regression analysis, coefficient of determination testing, and hypothesis testing.

IV. RESULTS

Validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not (Ghozali, 2018:51). In this study, the total number of samples (n) is 100 respondents, and the degrees of freedom (df) are calculated using the formula $df = n - 2$, resulting in $df = 100 - 2 = 98$. With $df = 98$ and a significance level of 0.05 (5%), the critical r table value is 0.165. The following are the results of the validity test using IBM SPSS Statistics 25:

Table 1. Validity test results

Variable	Items	r value	r table	Sig. (0.05)	Information
Influencer Marketing (X1)	X1.1	0,785	0,165	0,000	Valid
	X1.2	0,823	0,165	0,000	Valid
	X1.3	0,725	0,165	0,000	Valid
	X1.4	0,723	0,165	0,000	Valid
	X1.5	0,845	0,165	0,000	Valid
	X1.6	0,687	0,165	0,000	Valid
Product Innovation (X2)	X2.1	0,737	0,165	0,000	Valid
	X2.2	0,714	0,165	0,000	Valid
	X2.3	0,755	0,165	0,000	Valid
	X2.4	0,589	0,165	0,000	Valid
	X2.5	0,814	0,165	0,000	Valid
	X2.6	0,734	0,165	0,000	Valid
	X2.7	0,791	0,165	0,000	Valid
	X2.8	0,711	0,165	0,000	Valid
	X2.9	0,820	0,165	0,000	Valid
	X2.10	0,839	0,165	0,000	Valid
	X2.11	0,586	0,165	0,000	Valid
	X2.12	0,789	0,165	0,000	Valid
Purchase Decisions (Y)	Y1.1	0,623	0,165	0,000	Valid
	Y1.2	0,745	0,165	0,000	Valid
	Y1.3	0,664	0,165	0,000	Valid
	Y1.4	0,779	0,165	0,000	Valid
	Y1.5	0,777	0,165	0,000	Valid
	Y1.6	0,641	0,165	0,000	Valid
	Y1.7	0,688	0,165	0,000	Valid
	Y1.8	0,779	0,165	0,000	Valid
	Y1.9	0,712	0,165	0,000	Valid
	Y1.10	0,652	0,165	0,000	Valid
	Y1.11	0,633	0,165	0,000	Valid
	Y1.12	0,447	0,165	0,000	Valid
	Y1.13	0,714	0,165	0,000	Valid
	Y1.14	0,685	0,165	0,000	Valid

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Based on table 1 above, the results of the validity test show that all statement items used to measure the variables influencer marketing (X1), product innovation (X2), and purchase decision (Y) are valid. This is evidenced by the fact that all items for each variable have calculated r values greater than the r table value (0.165) with a significance level < 0.05 .

Respondents' answers to statements are considered reliable if each question is answered consistently. According to Riyanto & Hatmawan (2020:175), a variable is considered reliable if it has a Cronbach's Alpha (α) > 0.70 ; conversely, if Cronbach's Alpha (α) < 0.70 , the variable is considered not reliable. The following are the results of the reliability test using IBM SPSS Statistics 25:

Table 2. Reliability test results

Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Standard	Information
Influencer Marketing (X1)	0,857	0,70	Reliable
Product Innovation (X2)	0,922	0,70	Reliable
Purchase Decisions (Y)	0,899	0,70	Reliable

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Based on table 2 above, the results of the reliability test show that all variables have Cronbach’s Alpha values greater than 0.70. These results indicate that the items for the variables influencer marketing (X1), product innovation (X2), and purchase decision (Y) are considered trustworthy and reliable as measurement instruments for the variables used in this study.

According to Ghozali (2018:161), the normality test aims to examine whether, in a regression model, the disturbance or residual variable has a normal distribution.

Figure 1. Normality test results

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 25 (2025)

Based on the results of the normality test using the normal probability plot, the influence of influencer marketing and product innovation on purchase decisions meets the assumptions of normality. This conclusion is drawn based on the decision-making criteria in the normality test, which state that if the data points are distributed around the diagonal line and follow the direction of the diagonal line, or if the histogram shows a pattern resembling a normal distribution, then the regression model satisfies the assumption of normality Riyanto & Hatmawan (2020:137-138).

According to Ghozali (2018:107), the multicollinearity test aims to examine whether there is a correlation among the independent variables in the regression model. A good regression model should not exhibit multicollinearity between independent variables. The results of the multicollinearity test in this study are presented in the following table:

Table 3. Multicollinearity test results

Model	Collinearity		Information
	Tolerance	VIF	
Influencer Marketing (X1)	0,278	3,592	No Multicollinearity Occurs
Product Innovation (X2)	0,278	3,592	No Multicollinearity Occurs

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Based on table 3 above, the results of the multicollinearity test show that the VIF values for the variables influencer marketing and product innovation have tolerance values greater than 0.10 and VIF values less than 10. Therefore, it can be concluded that the independent variables do not exhibit multicollinearity.

The heteroscedasticity test aims to examine whether there is an inequality in the variance of the residuals from one observation to another in a regression model (Ghozali, 2018:137). If the variance of the residuals remains constant across observations, it is referred to as homoscedasticity; if it differs, it is called heteroscedasticity. A good regression model is one that exhibits homoscedasticity or does not show signs of heteroscedasticity. The results of the heteroscedasticity test in this study are presented in the following figure:

Figure 2. Heteroscedasticity test results

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 25 (2025)

Based on figure 2 above, the results of the heteroscedasticity test show that the data points are scattered above and below the value of 0 on the Y-axis. Therefore, it can be concluded that the regression model does not exhibit heteroscedasticity.

To confirm the existence of an influence between the independent variables and the dependent variable, this study employs multiple regression analysis, in which the independent variables are Influencer Marketing (X1) and Product Innovation (X2), and the dependent variable (Y) is Purchase Decision. The following presents the results of data processing using IBM SPSS Statistics 25:

Table 4. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test Results

Model	B
(Constant)	0,234
Influencer Marketing (X1)	0,738
Product Innovation (X2)	0,699

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Based on the results of the multiple linear regression analysis, among the variables Influencer Marketing (X1) and Product Innovation (X2), the variable that contributes the most or has the greatest influence on Purchase Decision (Y) is Influencer Marketing (X1) with a coefficient of 0.738, compared to Product Innovation (X2) with a coefficient of 0.699.

According to Ghozali (2018:97), the coefficient of determination (R^2 test) aims to measure how well the model explains the variation of the dependent variable. The following presents the results of data processing using IBM SPSS Statistics 25:

Table 5. Results of Determination Coefficient Analysis

Model	Adjusted (R^2)
1	0,554

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Based on table 5 above, the results of the coefficient of determination (R^2) analysis show that the Adjusted R Square value obtained is 0.554. This means that the multiple coefficient of determination (R^2) is 0.554, indicating that 55.4% of the variation in purchase decisions at the fashion MSMEs Veilish.chic in Tulungagung Regency is influenced by influencer marketing (X1) and product innovation (X2), while the remaining 44.6% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

According to Ghozali (2018:98–99), the partial test or t-test essentially indicates how far a single explanatory/independent variable individually or partially explains the variation in the dependent variable.

Table 6. t-test results

Variable	t _{value}	t _{table}	Sig.	significance level 5%	Information
Influencer Marketing (X1)	2,105	1,984	0,038	0,05	Significant
Product Innovation (X2)	4,009	1,984	0,000	0,05	Significant

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Based on table 6, the results of the partial hypothesis testing (t-test) can be concluded as follows:

1. H_a for Hypothesis 1 is accepted and H_0 is rejected, because the variable Influencer Marketing has a t-value > t-table, namely $2.105 > 1.984$, and a significance level lower than 5%, namely $0.038 < 0.05$. Based on these criteria, it can be concluded that Hypothesis (H_1) stating that influencer marketing partially has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions at the fashion MSMEs Veilish.chic in Tulungagung Regency is accepted.
2. H_a for Hypothesis 2 is accepted and H_0 is rejected, because the variable Product Innovation has a t-value > t-table, namely $4.009 > 1.984$, and a significance level lower than 5%, namely $0.000 < 0.05$. Based on these criteria, it can be concluded that Hypothesis (H_2) stating that product innovation partially has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions at the fashion MSMEs Veilish.chic in Tulungagung Regency is accepted.

According to Riyanto and Hatmawan (2020:142–143), the F-test is used to measure the extent to which the independent variables collectively influence the dependent variable.

Table 7. F-test results

F _{value}	F _{table}	Significance	Significance level 5%	Information
62,564	3,090	0,000	0,05	Significant

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Based on table 7 above, the results of the simultaneous hypothesis testing (F-test) indicate that H_a for Hypothesis 3 is accepted and H_0 is rejected, because the F-value > F-table, namely $62.564 > 3.090$, and the significance level < 5%, namely $0.000 < 0.05$. Based on these criteria, it can be concluded that Hypothesis (H_3) stating that influencer marketing and product innovation simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions at the fashion MSMEs Veilish.chic in Tulungagung Regency is accepted.

V. DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the partial hypothesis testing, it can be concluded that the influencer marketing variable has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. This finding is supported by the t-test results showing that the t-value > the t-table ($2.105 > 1.984$) and the significance level < 5% ($0.038 < 0.05$). These results are in accordance with the initial hypothesis stating that influencer marketing is presumed to have a positive influence on purchase decisions at the fashion MSMEs Veilish.chic in Tulungagung Regency. This result supports previous research conducted by Artanti et al. (2024) entitled "Dimensions of Influencer Marketing Engagement, EWOM (Electronic Word of Mouth), and Online Customer Rating on Purchase Decisions of Muslim Fashion Products on Shopee E-commerce." The study found that influencer marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. Based on all the data obtained, it can be stated that influencer marketing positively affects purchase decisions at the fashion MSMEs Veilish.chic in Tulungagung Regency. To maximize the effectiveness of influencer marketing, it is important for Veilish.chic to be more selective in collaborating with influencers by considering criteria in line with the key indicators of influencer marketing. These include the influencer's ability to convey convincing information to the audience, act as a credible source of product knowledge, and possess appeal in terms of creativity in content creation as well as friendliness in communication and message delivery. In addition, it is essential for Veilish.chic to choose influencers who have high levels of engagement on social media and are experts in promoting fashion products, so that their followers align with Veilish.chic's target market. This will ensure that promotional messages are delivered more accurately and effectively.

Based on the results of the partial hypothesis testing, it can be concluded that the product innovation variable has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. This is supported by the t-test results showing that the t-value is greater than the t-table ($4.009 > 1.984$) and the significance value is lower than 5% ($0.000 < 0.05$). These findings are consistent with the initial hypothesis, which proposed that product innovation positively influences purchase decisions at the fashion MSMEs Veilish.chic in Tulungagung Regency. This result supports previous research conducted by Nicholas et al. (2024), entitled "Analysis of the Influence of Product Quality, Brand Image, Lifestyle, and Product Innovation on Consumer Purchase Decisions at Uniqlo (Case Study of Consumers in Pekanbaru City)." The study found that product innovation has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. Based on all the data obtained, it can be stated that product innovation positively influences purchase decisions at the fashion MSMEs Veilish.chic in Tulungagung Regency. To maximize the effectiveness of product innovation, it is recommended that Veilish.chic

continuously generate new ideas by regularly updating designs and keeping up with the latest fashion trends without neglecting market needs. Furthermore, improving material quality and maintaining consistency in preserving the brand's unique characteristics are also crucial to ensure that Veilish.chic remains competitive and appealing in both local and national markets.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the research findings and discussions presented in the previous chapter regarding the influence of influencer marketing and product innovation on purchase decisions at the fashion MSMEs Veilish.chic in Tulungagung Regency, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Influencer marketing has a positive and significant partial effect on purchase decisions. This means that to increase purchase decisions, it is necessary to implement effective influencer marketing strategies by focusing on aspects such as trustworthiness, expertise, and attractiveness.
2. Product innovation has a positive and significant partial effect on purchase decisions. This implies that to improve purchase decisions, continuous product innovation is required, taking into account aspects such as new product development, new product lines, additions to existing product lines, improvements to existing products, and cost reductions.
3. Influencer marketing and product innovation simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. This indicates that, in order to enhance purchase decisions, the company should integrate effective influencer marketing strategies with ongoing product innovation.

VII. SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of this study, the following suggestions can be provided to Veilish.chic MSMEs based on respondent answers with the lowest scores:

1. To enhance purchase decisions through influencer marketing strategies, Veilish.chic should collaborate with influencers who possess the ability to convey product-related information accurately. It is important for Veilish.chic to carefully select influencers who are not only visually appealing but also have a strong understanding of fashion products and are able to communicate information in an informative, honest, and convincing manner.
2. To increase purchase decisions through expanded product innovation, Veilish.chic is advised to strengthen the promotion and identity of new product lines through engaging marketing content, such as product review videos, behind-the-scenes production processes, and customer testimonials, to introduce new product lines that may not yet be widely recognized by the audience.
3. In addition, to improve purchase decisions, particularly in terms of consumer purchase timing, Veilish.chic should consider hosting regular live shopping sessions to create direct interaction with the audience and build real-time purchase urgency through limited stock information. Implementing a customer loyalty program (loyalty rewards) is also recommended to encourage repeat purchases.

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